

Mixed Ligand Complexes : Part I. O-phenanthroline Bis Biguanide Cobalt (III) and $\alpha\alpha'$ -Dipyridyl Bis Biguanide Cobalt (III) Salts*

R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar

Cis diamine bis biguanide Co(III) cation reacts readily with the heterocyclic bases, O-phenanthroline or $\alpha\alpha'$ -Dipyridyl with liberation of ammonia. The resulting heterochelates, O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) and $\alpha\alpha'$ -Dipyridyl bis biguanide Co(III) have been isolated in the form of a large number of salts including the Chloride-d-tartrate. The complexes have been characterised through conductance measurements, equivalent weight determinations and electronic absorption spectra. Two absorption bands around 35000 cm^{-1} and 21000 cm^{-1} are typical of Cobalt(III) complexes.

The Chloride-d-tartrate salts have been fractionally crystallised and the pure dextro and levo diastereoisomers isolated. Resolution is normal and complete. Sulphate salts of the optically active d and l forms have also been characterised. Rotation characteristics are ;

No racemisation occurs in aqueous solution at 35°C or on heating the solid crystalline materials to 120°C.

This series of studies emanates from our search for a number of kinetically inert robust Co(III) and Cr(III) complexes which could be subjected to detailed kinetic and resolution studies. The literature in this regard is not extensive. Most of the inert mixed ligand or strictly speaking heterochelate complexes of Co(III) have been built up on the skeleton of Co(III) bis ethylenediamine and propylene diamine and these have been subjected to numerous studies.¹⁻¹¹

A Summary of the works described in this and the next two papers was presented before the Joint Convention of the Indian Chemical Society and the C.S.I.R. held at Aligarh, December 25-29, 1965.

1. Htdaka and Douglas, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1180.
2. Lui and Douglas, *ibid.*, 1964, 3, 1356.
3. Werner and Mattsen, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1918, 1, 78.
4. Werner, Schwyzer and Karrer, *ibid.*, 1921, 4, 115.
5. Bailar and Anten, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 774.
6. Bailar, Jonelis and Huffmann, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 2224.
7. Dwyer, Sargason and Rold, *ibid.*, 1963, 85, 1215.
8. Bushra and Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 137.
9. Warner and Basahart, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2178.
10. McCullough and Bailar, 1956, 78, 714.
11. Murakami *et. al.*, *Chem. Abst.*, 1963, 58, 13406.

Since our undertaking of this broad programme some reports have appeared in the literature on the Co(III) heterochelates of O-phenanthroline and $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl.¹¹⁻¹³

In this first paper of the series we report the synthesis, characterisation and resolution of O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) and $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl bis biguanide Co(III) salts. Both O-phenanthroline¹ $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl and biguanide are extremely powerful and formidable coordinating ligands and have played important roles in elucidating many interesting aspects of complex chemistry. Besides stabilising many otherwise unfamiliar oxidation states of metal ions¹⁴⁻¹⁶ these ligands have played significant roles in the development of ideas on the mechanism of racemisation. The racemisation rate, for example, of $[\text{Ni}(\text{O-phen})_2]^{++}$ is the same as the corresponding rate of dissociation and these observations have lent support to the dissociation mechanism of racemisation process¹⁶. On the other hand $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2]^{+++}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{Ph-BigH})_2]^{+++}$ (BigH = Biguanide, and Ph. BigH = Phenyl Biguanide) are believed to undergo racemisation through an intramolecular mechanism.¹⁷⁻¹⁸

We therefore decided to bring together these two interesting types of ligands inside the same coordination zone around Co(III) and to study the properties of the resulting heterochelates. These studies added some further enthusiasm because of the failure to effect resolution of $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})_2]^{++}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})_2]^{++}$. This failure has been attributed to the presence of traces of Co(II) complex which initiates a fast electron-transfer racemisation.^{19-19(a)}

In order to effect such synthesis of heterochelate complexes of the bis biguanide type we had recourse to the complex cis diamine bis biguanide Co(III) described a number of years ago²⁰. We found this material responding ideally to our synthetic requirement. Thus the cis diamine complex reacted very rapidly with the heterocyclic bases such as O-phenanthroline & $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl liberating ammonia and finally providing the mixed ligand complexes²¹. Whereas the cis

12. Ablov and Palade, *Chem. Abst.*, 1963, 58, 4133.
13. Kleinberg, *Unfamiliar Oxidation States and their Stabilization*.
14. Cotton & Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers.
15. Ray, *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, 61, 313.
16. Basolo and Pearson, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", p. 262.
17. Ray and Dutt, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 298; 1943, 20, 81.
18. Siddhanta. Dutt and Ray, *ibid.*, 1950, 27, 641.
19. Basolo and Pearson. "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", p. 288.
- 19(a) $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})_2]^{++}$ has since been resolved. cf : Lee *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1397.
20. Ray and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 4.
21. A preliminary notice of this synthetic route appeared in *Science and Culture*, 1964, 30, 549.

diamine reacted quite readily at the prevailing room temperature, the corresponding trans diamine complex responded rather slowly, though the trans-cis isomerisation did proceed on warming. The sulphate salt of the complex bases were obtained in the form of beautiful crystalline red coloured materials.

By metathetic reactions a large number of salts of the complex cations namely, the Chloride, Bromide, Iodide, Nitrate, and Oxalate have been obtained in highly crystalline forms. The complex bases have been obtained by the addition of alkali to the aqueous solution of the corresponding chloride salts. The bases rapidly absorb carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and liberate ammonia from ammonium salts.

TABLE I

Measurement of conductance in aqueous solution (temperature - 35°).

1. $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$

Dilutions (in litres)	128	256	512	1024
Λ^v	116.0	124.3	137.0	154.6
Λ^∞	137.28	140.43	149.57	164.62

Λ^∞ (Mean) = 147.9; Molar conductance = 443 Mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$

2. $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Molar conductance = 456 Mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$

3. $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Molar conductance = 495 Mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$

4. $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Molar conductance = 464 Mhos. $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$

The Λ^∞ values were calculated by Walden formula $\Lambda^\infty = \Lambda^v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v)$

where Λ^v = the equivalent conductance at a definite dilution.

v = dilution in litres, n_1 and n_2 the valencies of the ions.

The conductance values are somewhat outside the range (380–432 Mhos at .001 M and at 25°C)²² of a strong tri-univalent electrolyte. These high values may easily be ascribed to the prevailing high temperature at which the measurements were taken. The equivalent weights of the complex chloride and the nitrate salts were evaluated by running the aqueous solutions through a strong cation exchanger (H^+ form) and by titrating the liberated acid. The values are in good agreement with those arrived at from the analytical and conductance results.

The electronic absorption spectra of the two heterochelates have also been studied within the range 330 $m\mu$ to 550 $m\mu$.

TABLE II

Equivalent weight values.

Complex	Equivalent weight	
	Required	Found
1. [Cl(O-phen)(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	182	187
2. [Co(O-phen)(BigH) ₂](SO ₄) _{1.5} 5H ₂ O	224	222
3. [Co(dipy)(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ 3H ₂ O	192	188
4. [Co(dlpy)(BigH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ H ₂ O	206	198

TABLE III

Absorption spectral characteristics.

Complex	Band II			Band I		
	λ_{max} (m μ)	ν W. number (cm ⁻¹)	Molar ϵ	λ_{max} (m μ)	W. number (cm ⁻¹)	Molar ϵ
[Co(O-phen)(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	335	30,000	1350	470	21,210	177
[Co(dipy)(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ 3H ₂ O	330	30,300	1145	465- 470	21,500- 21,300	172
[Co(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	350- 355	28,600- 28,200	220	475	21,100	235

These studies provide two absorption bands around 30000 cm⁻¹ and 21000 cm⁻¹. These bands are typical of Co(III) complexes and represent the tran-

The short wave length bands exhibit very high molar extinction coefficients which are partly due to the absorption of the heterocyclic bases around these wave lengths. On comparing the absorption bands with the homochelate trisbiguanide Co(III), the bands appeared to be shifted to a somewhat higher frequency side, being indicative of slightly stronger ligand-fields set by O-phenanthroline and $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl.

Besides characterising a number of salts of common anions, salts with optically active anions such as d-tartrate have also been prepared and characterised. The chloride-d-tartrate salts of both the series have been fractionally crystallised and the two diastereoisomers separated. The first few crops gave constant dextro rotations followed by one or two crops with poor rotation and again the last few fractions gave constant levo rotations. The first few crops and the last few crops were again mixed separately and their aqueous solutions fractionated

further, with practically no improvement in the rotation values. Thus the separation of the diastereoisomers was quite normal and complete. Unlike the resolution of tris biguanide Co(III) through the chloride-d-tartrate, no evidence of equilibrium dependant asymmetric transformation of the second order was observed. Metathetical reactions with ammonium sulphate provided the two enantiomers namely, (+) and (-) $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{O-phen})](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ aq. and $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{dipy})](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ aq. Both the diastereoisomers and the enantiomers are quite stable in aqueous solution at room temperature for at least a week. No racemisation occurs on heating of the samples in the solid crystalline state to 120°C. Synthesis of other salts of the active cation was not attempted because of limited availability of the heterocyclic ligands.

TABLE IV

Complex	Specific rotation	Molar rotation	Temperature
1. (a) d $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]_d\text{-tart}$ $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Cl	(+) 383°	(+) 2727°	36°C
(b) l $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]_l\text{-tart}$ $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Cl	(-) 400°	(-) 2776°	36°C
2. (a) d $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(+) 362°	(+) 2371°	36°C
(b) l $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(-) 387°	(-) 2500°	36°C
3. (a) d $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]_d\text{-tart}$ $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Cl	(+) 612°	(+) 3880°	36°C
(b) l $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]_l\text{-tart}$ $2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Cl	(-) 587°	(-) 3774°	36°C
4. (a) d $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(+) 644°	(+) 3831°	36°C
(b) l $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(-) 612°	(-) 3806°	36°C
5. (a) d $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2]_d\text{-tart}$ $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Cl	(+) 340°	(+) 2161°	31°C
(b) l $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2]_l\text{-tart}$ $5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Cl	(-) 335°	(-) 2129°	31°C
6. (a) d & l $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ $3.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(+) 362.5°	(±) 2062°	31°C

Optical rotations were measured in a student model Carl Zeiss Polarimeter, giving reading upto $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Accuracy of the above rotation values are limited because of only moderate accuracy that the Polarimeter offered and also because of the limitations offered by the coloured Co(III) solutions (0.2% solution).

The phenanthroline complex has been found to give a significantly higher rotation as compared to tris biguanide complex. The dipyriddy biguanide mixed complex again records a much larger rotation compared to the phenanthroline complex. The lower rotation of the phenanthroline complex may be attributed to a higher rigidity compared to α , α' -dipyriddy. The least soluble fractions of the chloride-d-tartrates being dextro rotatory conform to Werner's generalisation that the chloride-d-tartrate of the dextro cation always form the least soluble fraction. In the case of the tris biguanide complex the levo cation, however, form the less

soluble chloride-d-tartrate. This optical rotatory dispersion as also circular dichroism studies are expected to offer interesting information about the generic configuration of these heterochelates.

We have undertaken detailed experimental studies on the racemisation paths of the active complexes. These will be reported in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL

Biguanide acid sulphate was prepared according to standard procedure²³. Cis diamine bis biguanide Co(III) base and sulphate salts were prepared as described later²⁴. The trans diamine bis biguanide Co(III) Hydroxide sulphate was prepared according to the published procedure²⁵.

1. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) sulphate*: The diamine base (1 gm.) and *O-phenanthroline* monohydrate (.6 gm.) were suspended in water (10-15 ml) when there was a slow evolution of ammonia in the cold. The mixture was digested on the steam bath till it was free from ammonia. As the reaction proceeded, woolly precipitate separated out. Some more water (5-6 ml.) was added and the suspension was neutralised in the cold with dil. H₂SO₄. At first a sparingly soluble red precipitate appeared, though the solution was alkaline (indicative of the formation of the hydroxide sulphate) which gradually dissolved out on neutralisation to pH 6.5. The solution was concentrated on a steam bath and cooled in ice and the crystals filtered at the pump. The crystals were then dissolved in minimum volume of water on a steam bath and slowly cooled in a refrigerator over-night and the crystals filtered, washed with alcohol and air dried. Found: Co, 8.58; N, 25.00; SO₄, 20.94; H₂O (at 120°), 14.7%; [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂](SO₄)_{1.5} · 5H₂O requires, Co, 8.7; N, 24.90; SO₄, 21.38; H₂O, 13.3%.

2. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride*: It was prepared in a similar way like the sulphate salt by using dilute HCl instead of dilute H₂SO₄. Found: Co, 10.64; N, 31.0; Cl, 18.7% [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂]Cl₃ requires, Co, 10.8; N, 30.8; Cl, 19.4%.

3. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) base*: *O-phenanthroline* bis biguanide Co(III) chloride (1 gm.) was dissolved in a minimum volume of water (10-12 ml.) and was treated with 6N NaOH when dull red coloured woolly crystals separated. When the mixture was distinctly alkaline it was cooled in ice for half an hour in a stoppered flask and filtered at the pump, and washed well with ice cold water to free it from NaOH and was dried in a KOH desiccator. Found: Co, 11.3; N, 33.0; H₂O, (at 120°), 4.6% [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂](OH)₃ · 1.5 H₂O requires, Co, 11.4, N, 32.5; H₂O, 5.2%.

The complex base liberates ammonia from ammonium salts on warming.

23. Dunn, 'The Visible and ultraviolet spectra of complex compounds' in "Modern Coordination Chemistry" by Lewis & Wilkinson, Interscience Publishers, 1960.
24. Inorganic Syntheses, Part VI, p. 65.
25. Dutta and Sarkar, this series, this Journal, under publication.

4. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Iodide* : The *O*-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) chloride (1 gm.) was dissolved in the minimum volume of water on a steam bath and treated with a concentrated solution of KI. Almost immediately the sparingly soluble iodide salt began to separate out in the form of bright yellowish red crystals. The solution was cooled in a refrigerator overnight and the crystals were filtered, washed with alcohol and air dried. } Found : Co, 7.0 ; N, 19.5 ; I, 45.6 ; H₂O (at 120°), 3.2% [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂]₂I₂ · 1.5 H₂O requires, Co, 6.9 ; N, 19.8 ; I, 44.9 ; H₂O, 3.1%.

5. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Nitrate* : Obtained similarly like the iodide by using ammonium nitrate instead of KI. } Found : Co, 9.0 ; N, 31.5 ; H₂O (at 120°), 6.6% [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂](NO₃)₂ · 2.5 H₂O requires, Co, 8.8 ; N, 31.3 ; H₂O, 6.7%.|

6. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Oxalate* : The *O*-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride (1 gm.) was dissolved on a steam bath in a minimum volume of water and was treated with an almost saturated solution of ammonium oxalate. On concentration on water bath crystals began to separate out. On cooling in ice the oxalate salt of the complex separated together with ammonium oxalate. These were filtered and redissolved on a steam bath in a minimum volume of water and allowed to cool at room temperature, when shining red crystals began to separate out. These were filtered, washed with cold water and air dried. } Found : N, 26.4 ; H₂O (at 120°), 11.19% [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂](C₂O₄)_{1.5} · 4H₂O requires N, 26.00 ; H₂O, 11.19%.|

7. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Hydroxide sulphate* : The trans diamine hydroxide sulphate (.5 gm.) and *O*-phenanthroline mono hydrate (.25 gm.) were treated with water (15 ml.). The mixture was heated on a steam bath when evolution of ammonia occurred. When all the ammonia was driven out, the precipitate was dissolved out on a steam bath by the addition of more water. The solution was filtered, concentrated and finally cooled when red scales separated out. The red crystals were filtered and washed with alcohol and air dried. } Found : N, 28.7 ; SO₄, 16.31 ; H₂O, (at 120°), 5.6% [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂]₂SO₄ · 2H₂O requires N, 28.5 ; SO₄, 16.4, H₂O, 6.1%.|

8. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride d-tartrate* : Na-d-tartrate (.45 gm.) and silver nitrate (.68 gm.) were dissolved separately in water (10-12 ml.) and the silver nitrate solution was added to that of the Na-d-tartrate when there was an immediate precipitation of the silver d-tartrate. The precipitate was filtered and washed with ice cold water. The Na-d-tartrate was then dissolved in cold water (400 ml.) and a solution of *O*-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) chloride (1.09 gm.) in water (15-20 ml.) was added to it with stirring. There was an immediate precipitation of AgCl. The solution was allowed to stand for half an hour and was filtered free from AgCl. The procedure was repeated for 5 gms. of the chloride taking 1 gm. each time.

The solution thus obtained was evaporated on a steam bath just to dryness and was taken up with aqueous alcohol and filtered out. } Found : Co, 8.6 ; N, 33.7 ; Cl, 4.2 ; H₂O (at 120°), 12.0% } [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂]d-tart 5H₂O requires, Co, 8.0 ; N, 23.5 ; Cl, 4.9 ; H₂O, 12.6%. }

9. *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) d-camphor sulphonate* : *O-phenanthroline bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride* (1 gm.) was dissolved on a steam bath in a minimum volume of water and to this solution a solution of ammonium d-camphor sulphonate (1 gm.) was added when there was an immediate precipitation of the camphor sulphonate salt of the complex. The product was digested on the steam bath for 1-2 minutes, and then cooled in ice, filtered, washed with cold water and air dried. } Found : Co, 5.0 ; N, 14.2 ; H₂O (at 120°), 5.0% } [Co(O-phen)(BigH)₂](CS₃) requires, Co, 4.9 ; N, 14.0 ; H₂O, 5.2%. }

The different salts for the dipyriddy complex were obtained by following similar procedure as done with the corresponding *O-phenanthroline* complex.

10. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Sulphate* : } Found : Co, 9.4 ; N, 27.5 ; SO₄, 22.9 ; H₂O (at 120°) 8.9% : [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂](SO₄)_{1.5} 3.5H₂O requires Co, 9.4 ; N, 27.00 ; SO₄, 23.1 ; H₂O, 10.1%. }

11. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride* : } Found : Co, 10.7 ; N, 30.0 ; Cl, 18.2 ; H₂O (at 120°) 9.9% : [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂]Cl₃ 3H₂O requires, Co, 10.2 ; N, 29.2 ; Cl, 18.4 ; H₂O 9.3%. }

12. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Hydroxide* : } Found : Co, 10.5 ; N, 30.5 ; H₂O (at 120°) 5.5% ; [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂](OH)₃ 5H₂O requires, Co, 10.6 ; N, 30.2 ; H₂O, 16.1%. }

13. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Nitrate* : } Found : Co, 9.7 ; N, 34.0 ; H₂O (at 120°) 3.3% ; [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂](NO₃)₃ H₂O requires, Co, 9.5 ; N, 33.9 ; H₂O, 2.9%. }

14. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Bromide* : } Found : Co, 8.5 ; N, 24.0 ; Br, 34.5 ; H₂O (at 120°) 7.8% ; [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂]Br₃ 3H₂O requires, Co, 8.3 ; N, 23.6 ; Br, 33.8 ; H₂O, 7.6%. }

15. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Hydroxide Sulphate* : } Found : Co, 10.16 ; N, 28.8 ; SO₄, 16.71 ; H₂O (at 120°) 11.4% ; [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂]SO₄ 3.5 H₂O requires, Co, 9.9 ; N, 28.4 ; SO₄, 16.2 ; H₂O, 10.6%. }

16. *αα'-dipyriddy bis biguanide Co(III) Chloride-d-tartrate* : } Found Co, 8.6 ; N, 24.5 ; Cl, 4.9 ; H₂O (at 120°) 12.0% ; [Co(dipy)(BigH)₂]^{Cl}d-tart 4.5 H₂O requires, Co, 8.6 ; N, 24.7 ; Cl, 5.2 ; H₂O, 11.9%. }

The substance registered an almost zero rotation at the Na-D-Line.

Fractional crystallisation of the diastereoisomers: The racemic chloride d-tartrate (5 gm.) was dissolved with the aid of magnetic stirring at room temperature (35°) in water (about 350 ml.) to form a nearly saturated solution. After filtration the solution was allowed to crystallise under a fan. The first few crops, were dextro rotatory and after two more crops with poor (+) rotation and (–) rotation, the next few crops were again strongly levo rotatory. The first few and the last few crops were separately mixed and refractionated with no improvement on the original values.

A. O-phenanthroline series: (a) Found for the dextro diastereoisomer: $[\alpha]_D = (+) 383^\circ$; $[M]_D = (+) 2727^\circ$; ($t=36^\circ$). Found: H₂O, 12.0%; $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]_D\text{-tart}$ 5H₂O, requires, H₂O, 12.6%. Found for the anhydrous compound: Co, 9.2; N, 26.9%; $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]_D\text{-tart}$ requires, Co, 9.4; N, 27.0%. (b) Found for the levo diastereoisomers: $[\alpha]_D = (-) 400^\circ$; $[M]_D = (-) 2776^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$). Found: H₂O (at 120°) 10.0%; $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]_L\text{-tart}$ 4H₂O requires, H₂O, 10.3%. Found for the anhydrous compound: Co, 9.26; N, 26.2%; $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2]_L\text{-tart}$ requires, Co, 9.4; N, 27.0%.

The sulphate salts of the above optically active cations were obtained by trituration in the cold of the respective diastereoisomers with saturated solution of ammonium sulphate, filtered, washed with ice cold water and alcohol and dried in air.

(a) For the dextro: $[\alpha]_D = (+) 362^\circ$; $[M]_D = (+) 2371^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$). Found: N, 25.0; SO₄, 21.9; H₂O (at 120°) 10.8%; $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ 4H₂O requires, N, 25.6; SO₄, 21.9; H₂O, 10.9%. (b) For the levo: $[\alpha]_D = (-) 387^\circ$; $[M]_D = (-) 2500^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$). Found: Co, 9.5; N, 25.9; SO₄, 22.6; H₂O (at 120°) 10.0%; $[\text{Co}(\text{O-phen})(\text{BigH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ 3.5H₂O requires, Co, 9.1; N, 26.0; SO₄, 22.2; H₂O, 9.7%.

B. αα'-Dipyridyl series: (a) Found: for the dextro diastereoisomer: $[\alpha]_D = (+) 612^\circ$; $[M]_D = (+) 3880^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$). Found: H₂O (at 120°) 5.8%; $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]_D\text{-tart}$ 2H₂O requires, H₂O, 5.6%. Found for the anhydrous compound: Co, 9.9; N, 27.4%; $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]_D\text{-tart}$ requires, Co, 9.8; N, 28.0%. (b) Found for the levo diastereoisomer: $[\alpha]_D = (-) 587^\circ$; $[M]_D = (-) 3774^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$). Found: H₂O (at 120°) 6.9%; $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]_L\text{-tart}$ 2.5H₂O requires, H₂O, 7.0%. Found for the anhydrous compound: Co, 9.8; N, 27.4%; $[\text{Co}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})_2]_L\text{-tart}$ requires, Co, 9.8; N, 28.0%.

The sulphate salts of the above optically active cations were obtained by trituration in the cold of the respective diastereoisomers with saturated Ammonium sulphate solution, filtered, washed with ice cold water, and alcohol and air dried.

(a) For the dextro $[\alpha]_D = (+) 644^\circ$ $[M]_D = (+) 3831^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$).
 {Found : N, 27.6 ; SO_4 , 24.0 ; H_2O (at 120°) 6.0% ; $[Co(dipy)(BigH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2H_2O$ requires, N, 28.2 ; SO_4 , 24.2 ; H_2O , 6.0%.}

(b) For the levo $[\alpha]_D = (-) 612^\circ$ $[M]_D = (-) 3806^\circ$ ($t=36^\circ$).
 {Found : N, 26.5 ; H_2O , (at 120°) 10.1% ; $[Co(dipy)(BigH)_2](SO_4)_{1.5} \cdot 3.5H_2O$ requires, N, 27.0 ; H_2O , 10.1%.}

GENERAL EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Cobalt was estimated as anhydrous cobalt sulphate, anions by usual methods and, nitrogen by semi micro combustion technique.

Equivalent weight was determined by running an aqueous solution of the complex through an ion exchange resin (amberlite, IR-120, H^+ form) column and then titrating the eluate with standard NaOH. Equivalent weight was given by the relation :

$$E.W. = \frac{W \times 36.5}{V \times S \times .001825}$$

Where W = weight of the substance in gm.

V = volume of alkali needed for titration of the liberated acid.

S = strength of alkali in N/20.

36.5 = molecular weight of HCl.

.001825 = gm. HCl per ml. of exactly N/20 solution.

Absorption spectra were taken with the help of Hilger watts Uvispek Spectrophotometer using 1 cm. cells.

Conductance was measured with a Phillips conductivity bridge.

This is a real pleasure to express our gratitude to M/S. North American Cyanamide Company for a very generous gift of dicyandiamide and to M/S. G. Fredrick Smith Chemical Company for $\alpha\alpha'$ -dipyridyl and O-phenanthroline. We record with appreciation the encouragement and facilities given to us by Professor S. K. Siddhanta.